

T = diameter of fungus colony (mm) in presence of test chemical after 96 h.

Results and Discussion

Most of the compounds reported herein have been screened for their antifungal activity against *A. flavus*, *H. oryzae* and *C. sacchari* and found to possess moderate to fairly good level of fungicidal activity. However, they are slightly more toxic against *C. sacchari* than *A. flavus* and *M. oryzae*. In general, introduction of different groups and their position did not affect the toxicity to any marked degree. However, introduction of methyl group resulted in an increase of fungicidal activity. A comparison of compounds of Tables 1-4 shows that the dibromides (VI) are little more active than compounds III which in turn show slightly better activity than compounds II. The least active are the compounds I (Table 1). Compounds 14 and 15 are more active due to the presence of bromine.

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Synthesis of Thiazolyl Compounds as Potential Fungicides

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THIAZOLES have been reported as insecticidal¹, antibacterial², antitubercular³, antifungal⁴, herbicidal⁵, pesticidal⁶ and local anaesthetic⁷ agents. Acridines have been reported as insecticides⁸ and fungicides⁹, and compounds containing triazole ring have shown fungicidal¹⁰, bactericidal¹¹ and pesticidal¹² activity. In view of these facts it was worth investigating the compounds having both the moieties.

2-Amino-4-phenylthiazole was condensed with 5-chloroacridine to yield 4-phenyl-2-(acridin-5-yl)aminothiazole (I). 4-Phenyl-(thiazol-2-yl)-aminoacetylhydrazine (VI) was reacted with 5-chloroacridine to yield *N*-(acridin-5-yl)-*N*'-(4''-phenylthiazole-2''-yl)-aminoacetylhydrazine (III). I on treatment with arylisothiocyanate yielded *N*-aryl-*N*'-(4''-phenylthiazol-2''-yl)aminoacetylthiosemicarbazide (IV) which on alkaline cyclisation yielded the corresponding triazole (V).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected and purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Structure of

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compounds were checked by elemental analyses, ir and nmr spectra. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 197 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Varian EM 360 spectrometer at 50 MHz.

4-Phenyl-2-(acridin-5-yl)-aminothiazoles (I): A DMF (20 ml) solution of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (0.01 M), 5-chloroacridine (0.01 M) and fused sodium acetate (2 g) was refluxed for 6 h, cooled and poured into water. The solid obtained was filtered, washed and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. The results of compounds thus prepared are given in Table 1.

N-(Acridin-5-yl)-N'-(4"-phenylthiazol-2"-yl)-aminoacetylhydrazine (III): A DMF (20 ml) solution of 5-chloroacridine (0.01 M), 4-phenyl-(thiazol-2-yl)-aminoacetylhydrazine (0.01 M) and pyridine (1 ml) was refluxed for 6 h, cooled and poured into water. The solid obtained was filtered, washed and

crystallised from aqueous ethanol. The results of compounds thus prepared are given in Table 2.

N-Aryl-N'-(4"-phenylthiazol-2"-yl)-aminoacetylthiosemicarbazide (IV): A methanolic solution of 4-phenylthiazol-2-yl-aminoacetylhydrazine (0.01 M) and arylisothiocyanate (0.01 M) was refluxed for 6 h and cooled. The solid obtained was filtered, washed and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. The results of compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 3.

3-(4'-Phenylthiazoyl-2'-yl)-aminoacetyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1, 2, 4-triazoles (V): N-Aryl-N'-(4"-phenylthiazol-2-yl)-aminoacetylthiosemicarbazide (0.01 M) was refluxed with NaOH solution (25 ml, 8%) for 5 h and poured into water and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave a solid, which was filtered, washed and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. The results of compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 4.

TABLE 1—4-PHENYL-2-(ACRIDIN-5'-YL)-AMINOTHIAZOLES (I)*

Sl. no.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Fungicidal activity, Conc. 10 ppm		
					<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
1.	H ^a	200d	95.6	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ S	29.7	29.5	30.6
2.	3-Cl ^b	210d	86.5	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ClN ₅ S	35.0	35.6	40.7
3.	1-CH ₃	225d	92.3	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ S	—	—	—
4.	3-CH ₃	185d	94.0	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ S	—	—	—

* Elemental analyses in good agreement with the calculated ones.

^a δ(DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₂) 4.2 (s, 1H, vinyl), 6.8 (s, 1H, NH) and 7.2-7.8 (m, 13H, Ar).

^b ν_{max} 3430 (NH secondary), 1580 (C = N conjugated cyclic), 750 (monosubst. benzene), 710 (—S—) and 620 cm⁻¹ (C—Cl).

TABLE 2—N-(ACRIDIN-5-YL)-N'-(4"-PHENYLTHIAZOL-2"-YL)-AMINOACETYLHYDRAZINES (III)

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Fungicidal activity, Conc. 10 ppm		
					<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
5.	—H	200 ^a	85.2	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ OS	32.2	32.7	33.3
6.	3-Cl	283	86.0	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ClN ₅ OS	—	—	—
7.	1-CH ₃ **	320	80.7	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ OS	—	—	—
8.	3-CH ₃	180 ^a	84.5	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ OS	40.4	40.5	43.7

* Explanation as in Table 1.

** ν_{max} 3440 (NH secondary), 1690 (CONH secondary), 1620 (C = N conjugated cyclic), 1385 (C—CH₃), 750 (monosubst. benzene) and 710 cm⁻¹ (—S—); δ(DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₂) 2.7 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.4 (s, 2H, NCH₂CO), 6.82 (m, 3H, NHHNCOCHNH) and 7.2-7.4 (m, 12H, Ar).

TABLE 3—N-ARYL-N'-(4"-PHENYLTHIAZOL-2"-YL)-AMINOACETYLTHIOSEMICARBAZIDES (IV)*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Fungicidal activity, Conc. 10 ppm		
					<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
9.	H	225	79.2	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ OS ₂	—	—	—
10.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ **	134	75.6	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₅ OS ₂	43.2	43.4	45.0
11.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	66	80.6	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₅ OS ₂	43.2	43.8	45.5

* Explanation as in Table 1.

** ν_{max} 3425 (NH secondary), 1700 (CONH secondary), 1600 (C = N conjugated cyclic), 1080 (C—S) and 170 cm⁻¹ (mono/*o*-subst. benzene).

TABLE 4—ARYL-N-(4"-PHENYLTHIAZOL-2'-YL)-AMINOMETHYL-4-ARYL-5-MERCAPTO-1,2,4-TRIAZOLES (V)*

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Molecular formula	Fungicidal activity, Conc. 10 ppm		
				<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>C. sacchari</i>
12.	—H**	68.5	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₅ S ₂	44.2	44.0	50.5
13.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	76.0	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₅ S ₂	—	—	—
14.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	75.6	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₅ S ₂	45.7	45.8	53.6
				75.5	78.3	72.8
				73.5	79.5	78.3

Memcg
Blitox 50 WP

* Explanation as in Table 1.

** ν_{max} 3400 (NH secondary), 2600 (SH), 1690 (C = N conjugated cyclic) and 760 cm⁻¹ (monosubst. benzene); δ(DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₂) 3.3 (s, 2H, CH₂), 6.6 (s, 1H, NH), 4.2 (s, 1H, vinyl) and 7.6-7.8 (m, 10H, Ar).

Fungicidal screening : The compounds were screened for antifungal activity against *A. flavus*, *H. oryzae* and *C. sacchhari* by agar plate technique^{1,2} at three different concentrations, viz. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. Two commercial fungicides Memege and Blitox 50 WP were also tested under similar conditions to compare the result. The number of replication in each case was three. The percentage inhibition of growth of fungus colony is given by the following expression.

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = \frac{C-T}{C} \times 100$$

where C=diameter of fungus colony (mm) in control after 96 h,

T=diameter of fungus colony (mm) in presence of test chemical after 96 h.

Results and Discussion

Most of the compounds screened possess moderate to fairly good level of fungicidal activity against all the three fungi showing more activity against *C. sacchhari*. Introduction of different groups and their position did not affect the toxicity to any marked degree. However, compounds containing CH₃ group were found to be more active than the unsubstituted compounds.

A comparison of thiazolyl compounds (Tables 1-4) shows the following order of antifungal activity.

compounds IV > compounds III > compounds II > compounds I. Highly active compounds of the series contain a thiazolyl and a triazolyl moiety.

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Alkaloid Contents of *Lupinus hartwegii* Roots

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LUPINUS hartwegii (Leguminosae), an annual herb, is a highly crossbred cultivar grown in gardens as winter ornamental^{1,2}. The plant has been investigated earlier by different workers for quinolizidine alkaloids³⁻⁵. No work has been reported so far on the roots of this species.

The present work deals with the isolation and characterisation of three quinolizidine and one indole alkaloid from the CHCl₃ extract of *L. hartwegii* roots.

Completely air dried and coarsely ground roots (500 g) were exhaustively extracted in a soxhlet extractor successively with petroleum ether (60-80°) and ethanol (95%). The ethanol extract was worked up with CHCl₃ by the usual procedure for the isolation of alkaloids⁶. The CHCl₃ extract, on column chromatography over neutral Al₂O₃ gave four alkaloids (compounds A-D), which were visualised on tlc plates by spraying iodoplatinate reagent⁶.

Compound A (aphylline) was crystallised from petroleum ether as colourless needles (30 mg), m.p. 99-101° (Lit.⁷ m.p. 100-101°); perchlorate, m.p. 233°; ν_{max} (KBr)⁸ 2970, 1640, 1455 and 1280 cm⁻¹; m/e^9 248 (M⁺), 247, 220, 137, 136, 98, 97, 96 and 84.

Compound B (lupanine) was crystallised from petroleum ether as colourless flakes (175 mg), m.p. 97-98°; perchlorate, m.p. 224°; co-tlc, m.m.p. and superimposable ir with an authentic sample confirmed the identity^{9,10}.

Compound C (nuttaline) was crystallised from acetone as colourless needles (35 mg), m.p. 107-109° (Lit.¹¹ m.p. 108-109°); perchlorate, m.p. 170-172°; ν_{max} (KBr)¹¹ 3480, 2810, 2760, 1650 and 1012 cm⁻¹; m/e^{12} 264 (M⁺), 246, 236, 154, 153, 152, 123, 84 and 55.

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